
ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL WORDS AND PHRASES

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colloquial words,
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textbook,
control,
task,
order,
deadline,
educational games.

ABSTRACT

Lexicology (along with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, and syntax serve as linguistic bases for working on words, phrases, and sentences. Connected speech is based on logic, literature, and the linguistics of complex syntactic integrity. The three directions are carried out in parallel, the vocabulary work provides material for the speech, the work on the word, the phrase and the sentence prepares for the connected speech. In turn, the connected story and essay serve as a means of enriching the vocabulary.

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The methodological requirement for developing students' speech is that the student is able to express his / her opinion, desire and necessity to express something orally or in writing is to create a situation that creates. Every speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be. Therefore, the second condition for developing students' speech is about the material of the speech exercises and to take care to make the student's speech meaningful. An idea is understood only if it is expressed in words, phrases, sentences, and speech that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful speech development is to equip speech with language tools. It is important to give students language samples and create good speaking conditions for them. Listening to speech and using it in one's own experience develops in children a conscious "language perception" based on teaching methods.

The methodological condition of speech development is to create a wide system of speech activity, that is, firstly, to understand a good speech pattern, and secondly, to create conditions for expressing one's opinion using the learned language tools.

The learners the language in the process of speaking. That's not enough, because it's superficial. There are a number of aspects of speech acquisition.

Room, letter, stem, bop, pleasant, both, generous, rare, common, color, customer, quality, demand, gospel, interlocutor, calm, weak, steamy, popular, cold-hearted, devshifat, etc.

A compound noun ending in (a) r, (-ness) and a compound adjective: substitute, equestrian.

A common noun and a common adjective denoting an object by comparing it with something else: trumpet, mushroom, horseradish, hybrid, sheryurak, almond, hawk such as.

A compound noun that expresses something on the basis of its color, taste, something in it, and so on: oleander, erysipelas, bitter gourd, etc.

A compound noun that means something has a purpose: a mountain, a desert, a water lily, a wolf.

The ceremony is a combination of the names of the cabins of the legend: the entrant, the bride, the bridegroom, the bridegroom, the bridegroom.

A compound noun formed by the transformation of a causative compound into a single word: thousandth, prefix, future.

A compound word that has been mastered from Russian or created by literal translation is added: cinema, radio station, camera, television, holiday.

All types of abbreviations and their suffixes are added: Tashkent State University, SamSU, etc. However, two adjacent abbreviations are written separately: Central Committee of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan (Central Council of the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan)

Double words and repetitions: slowly, melon-watermelon, house-to-house.

From year to year, such as roof-to-roof, the first part is in the exit agreement and the second part is in the direction agreement.

An isophalic compound is written separately. In this case, the suffix is added to the words ending in a consonant in the form of i, and the words ending in a vowel are added in the form of point of view, translation, etc. In Uzbek, words that are not used independently are added: lazy, sadness

Capitalization and spelling of abbreviations.

The person's name, patronymic, surname, nickname, symbolic name begin with a capital letter: Dilbar Urinova, Muhabbat Majidovna, Furkat, Navoi, Yilpigich.

The star and the planet, the famous name of another celestial body, begin with a capital letter: Hulkar, Sagittarius, Mirrix (name of stars and planets), Sea of Peace (name of relief on the Moon).

The name of a cultural and commercial enterprise, a work of literature and art, industrial and food products, as well as a vehicle, a sports facility begins with a capital letter: "Tong" hotel, "Soadat" company, "G ' uncha "kindergarten, the novel " Kutlug 'kan ", the statue of " Ozodlik ".

The first word in the name of an important historical date and holiday begins with a capital letter: Independence Day, Navruz, Eid al-Fitr.

Each word in the name of the state, the highest state organization and position, international organization is written in capital letters: the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Russian Federation, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the United Nations.

In another name, only the first word denoting the position is capitalized: Deputy Prime Minister, Writers' Union. The first word in the name of the ministry and department, enterprise and organization is written in capital letters: Ministry of Health, Academy of Sciences, Institute of Linguistics. Each word in the name of the highest state award is written in capital letters: the title of "Hero of Uzbekistan", the medal "Golden Star". Another award, the first word of which is written in capital letters: the order "For a Healthy Generation", the honorary title "Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan", the badge "Printing Excellence".

The first word of the sentence is written in capital letters: I took a look at the Bible from under the ground. (O. Yoqubov.)

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